

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

The impact of perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness on actual system use through intention to use as an intervening variable in subscription video on demand services (Study on Netflix users in Semarang City)

Annisa Puspitasari, Widayanto * and Hari Susanta Nugraha

Department of Business Administration, Faculty of Social and Political Science, Diponegoro University, Semarang, Indonesia.

World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2023, 18(03), 1354–1366

Publication history: Received on 16 May 2023; revised on 24 June 2023; accepted on 27 June 2023

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2023.18.3.1230>

Abstract

This study aims to determine the effect of perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness as independent variables on actual system use as the dependent variable through intention to use as an intervening variable on the Netflix subscription video on demand service. The population of this research is Netflix users who reside permanently or temporarily in Semarang City. The research was conducted through distributing questionnaires to a predetermined sample. The analysis was carried out by analyzing the outer model and inner model analysis on SmartPLS software. The results of this study are perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness have an influence on actual system use, both directly and indirectly. The mediating relationship of intention to use in influencing perceived ease of use on actual system use and perceived usefulness on actual system use is partial mediation. Suggestions that can be given to Netflix include continuing to develop its platform, meeting user needs with good product management, and paying attention to pricing strategies.

Keywords: Technology Acceptance Model; Perceived Ease of Use; Perceived Usefulness; Intention to Use; Actual System Use

1. Introduction

Internet users continue to increase every year. In Indonesia, internet users as of January 2022 reached 204.7 million or covering 73.7% of the total population of Indonesia. This figure is up 1.03% from the previous number of 202.6 million users in 2021. This increase was partly triggered by the increase in mobile devices, where the ratio of population to the number of mobile devices is 1:1.33, which means that the average Indonesian has more than 1 mobile device.

We Are Social notes that the third order of device usage is for watching television, for an average of 2 hours and 50 minutes, both in broadcast and streaming. Technological developments are changing consumer preferences(1), especially in Gen Z who no longer consider television as the main source of entertainment due to content on the internet that is easier to access(2). A survey conducted by GWI showed that watching videos, television broadcasts, and movies ranked as the fourth main reason for using the internet with a percentage of 51.5% of users. Changes in consumer preferences and the high growth in online video consumption have been capitalized on by content providers by launching subscription-based video on demand (SVOD) services, such as Netflix.

Netflix (Netflix, Inc) is one of the SVOD services that has the largest number of users in the world, including in Indonesia. Recorded in 2011-2021, the number of Netflix consumers in the world has increased every year, but in 2022 Netflix lost 200,000 subscribers during Q1 and 970,000 subscribers during Q2. This is the biggest drop in the history of Netflix.

* Corresponding author: Annisa Puspitasari, Widayanto

Some of the causes of the decline are user activity restriction policies, illegal subscribers, competition, and macro factors. Researchers conducted a pre-survey involving 30 respondents. The results of the pre-survey stated that Netflix users felt several problems, such as not being able to log in and log out, not being able to change passwords, account sharing problems, sudden video stops, missing subtitles, unstable video quality, incomplete movies, and less competitive prices. The problems felt by Netflix users are studied more deeply to determine their influence on interest in use which has implications for actual use. Based on the above phenomenon, researchers will conduct research with the title "The Impact of Perceived Ease of Use and Perceived Usefulness on Actual System Use through Intention to Use as an Intervening Variable in Subscription Video on Demand Services (Study on Netflix Users in Semarang City)".

Specifically, this study aims to prove and explain the hypotheses: [1] It is suspected that there is an influence between perceived ease of use on actual system use of Netflix subscription video on demand service, [2] It is suspected that there is an influence between intention to use on actual system use of Netflix subscription video on demand service, [3] It is suspected that there is an influence between perceived usefulness on actual system use of Netflix video on demand subscription service, [4] It is suspected that there is an influence between perceived ease of use on intention to use Netflix subscription video on demand service, [5] It is suspected that there is an influence between perceived usefulness on intention to use Netflix subscription video on demand service, [6] It is suspected that there is an influence between perceived ease of use on actual system use through intention to use on Netflix subscription video on demand service, and [7] It is suspected that there is an influence between perceived usefulness on actual system use through intention to use on Netflix subscription video on demand service.

2. Materials & Method

2.1. Technology Acceptance Model

The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) is a theory used to explain how people accept technology and use it in their daily lives(3). TAM is adapted from TRA or Theory of Reasoned Action developed by Fishbein & Ajzen(4), where TRA theory explains the social psychology theory model that explains the psychological factors that drive human behavior(5). The Technology Acceptance model developed by Davis(6) has five constructs, namely perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, attitude toward using, behavioral intention to use, and actual system use. This study eliminates the attitude toward using variable based on research conducted by previous researchers which states the results that the mediator variable attitude toward using does not have a significant effect between perceived usefulness and intention to use(6,7) or on actual system use(8). So that the variables used in this study are perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness of the independent variable, the intention to use variable as an intervening variable, and the actual system use variable as the dependent variable.

2.2. Perceived Ease of Use

Perceived ease of use is defined as the degree to which a person believes that using a system will free him from effort(6,9). There are four items used to measure perceived ease of use(9):

- Clear and understandable
Interaction between users and the system is clear and easy to understand
- Does not require a lot of mental effort
Users do not require much effort to interact with the system
- Easy to use
The system is easy to use or operate
- Easy to get the system to do what user wants to do
User can easily control the system

2.3. Perceived Usefulness

Perceived usefulness is defined as "the extent to which a person believes that using a system will improve their performance"(6,9). This is a development of the definition of "useful" itself, which is "the ability to be used profitably". There are four indicators that can be used to measure perceived usefulness(9):

- Improves job performance
Improves user performance in their activities.
- Increases productivity

Increase user productivity when doing their activities.

- Enhance job effectiveness
Improves user effectiveness in doing work.
- Useful
Has benefits to its users.

2.4. Intention to Use

Intention to use is a measure of the strength of a person's interest in performing certain behaviors, which in this case means the use of the system(4,7). Intention to use is defined as "a behavioral of people to keep using certain technology, the level of intention to use can be predicted by their behavior towards that certain technology (7). There are four indicators that can be used to measure intention to use:

- Intention to use a system
When someone has access to a system, they will tend to be interested in using the system.
- Prediction to use a system
When someone is given access to a system, it is likely that they will use the system.

2.5. Actual System Use

Actual system use is a person's external psychomotor response as measured by the actual use of the system(10). In other words, actual system use is when someone practices real behavior in adopting a system by using the system. System usage can be defined as how much time is used by users when interacting with the system and also the frequency of system use(11). In research conducted by Davis et al. (1989) system usage is measured using two questions related to frequency of use(7), so that in this study the indicators used to measure actual system use are:

- Frequency of use
User frequency in using the system.
- Duration of use
User duration in using the system.

2.6. Research Method

This research uses quantitative research type by distributing questionnaires with Likert scale to 97 respondents who use Netflix in Semarang City. The sampling technique used is non-probability sampling with the sampling method used is purposive sampling and accidental sampling. The criteria for respondents are aged 17-60, permanently or temporarily residing in Semarang City, have used Netflix services at least once in the past year, and use Netflix services through the website on the Windows operating system. Data analysis was carried out using SmartPLS 3.2.9 software which includes outer model analysis and inner model analysis. Outer model analysis includes convergent validity, discriminant validity, and reliability tests. Inner model analysis includes r-square, f-square effect size, and hypothesis testing.

Figure 1 Hypothesis Model

2.7. Hypothesis

2.7.1. *The Effect of Perceived Ease of Use on Actual System Use*

Davis (1989) through his research states that perceived ease of use has a significant positive effect on actual system use. Research conducted by Haryani et al. (2021) entitled “E-Travel Use in Padang: The Role of Enjoyment, Perceived Ease of Use, and Perceived Usefulness” shows the results that perceived ease of use has a positive and significant effect on actual system use(12). The results of research by Harta Tira et al. (2016) entitled “Application of the TAM Model to the Use of E-Newspaper in Denpasar City” also shows the results that perceived usefulness has a positive and significant effect on actual system use(13).

H1: It is suspected that there is an influence between perceived ease of use on actual system use of Netflix subscription video on demand service.

2.7.2. *The Effect of Intention to Use on Actual System Use*

Research by Andy et al., (2021) entitled “An Empirical Study to Validate the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) in Evaluating Desa Digital Application” states that intention to use has a positive and significant effect on actual system use(14). The results of research by Yuliana et al. (2022) entitled “Acceptance Analysis of School DAPODIK Information System Using the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)” also shows the results that perceived ease of use has a positive and significant effect on actual system use(15).

H2: It is suspected that there is an influence between intention to use on actual system use of the Netflix subscription video on demand service.

2.7.3. *The Effect of Perceived Usefulness on Actual System Use*

Research by Chairina (2021) entitled “The Effect of Perceived Ease of Use and Perceived Usefulness on Perceived Value and Actual Usage of Technology on Online Service of PT. Garuda Indonesia Tbk shows the results that perceived usefulness has a positive and significant effect on actual system use”(16). The results of research by Harta Tira et al. (2016) entitled “Application of the TAM Model to the Use of E-Newspaper in Denpasar City” also shows the results that perceived usefulness has a positive and significant effect on actual system use(13).

H3: It is suspected that there is an influence between perceived usefulness on the actual system use of the Netflix subscription video on demand service.

2.7.4. *The Effect of Perceived Ease of Use on Intention to Use*

Research by Sindarta & Santoso (2022) entitled “The Effect of Perceived Ease of Use on Intention to Use Through Perceived Usefulness of the Spotify Music Player Application among Android-based Smartphone Users states that perceived ease of use has a significant positive effect on intention to use” states that perceived ease of use has a significant positive effect on intention to use.(17). Similarly, research by Lee et al. (2019) entitled “Factors Affecting Over-The-Top Services: An Expanded Technology Acceptance Model” states that perceived ease of use has a positive influence on intention to use even though it is not significant(1).

H4: It is suspected that there is an influence between perceived ease of use on the intention to use the Netflix subscription video on demand service.

2.7.5. *The Effect of Perceived Usefulness on Intention to Use*

Research by Camilleri & Falzon (2021) entitled "Understanding Motivations to Use Online Streaming Services: Integrating The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) and The Uses and Gratifications Theory (UGT)" shows the results that perceived usefulness has a positive and significant effect on intention to use(18). The results of research by Sindarta & Santoso (2022) entitled "The Effect of Perceived Ease of Use on Intention to Use Through Perceived Usefulness of the Spotify Music Player Application among Android-based Smartphone Users" state that perceived usefulness has a significant positive effect on intention to use(17).

H5: It is suspected that there is an influence between perceived usefulness on the intention to use the Netflix subscription video on demand service.

2.7.6. The Effect of Perceived Ease of Use on Actual System Use through Intention to Use

According to research by Money & Turner (2004) which examines the Knowledge Management System, the intention to use variable is an important variable that can mediate perceived ease of use on actual system use(8). Research by Rahmawati & Narsa (2019) which examines AULA e-learning, intention to use acts as a partial mediating variable between perceived ease of use and actual system use(19).

H6: It is suspected that there is an influence between perceived ease of use on actual system use through intention to use on the Netflix video on demand subscription service.

2.7.7. The Effect of Perceived Usefulness on Actual System Use through Intention to Use

According to research by Money & Turner (2004) which examines the Knowledge Management System, the intention to use variable is an important variable that can mediate perceived usefulness on actual system use(8). Research by Rahmawati & Narsa (2019) which examines AULA e-learning, intention to use acts as a partial mediating variable between perceived usefulness and actual system use(19).

H7: It is suspected that there is an influence between perceived usefulness on actual system use through intention to use on the Netflix subscription video on demand service.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Convergent Validity

The outer loading analysis conducted shows the results of the loading factor numbers for all measuring items are above 0.7, which meets the validity requirements according to Fornell & Larcker (1981)(20).

Figure 2 Path Analysis Model Diagram

Table 1 Nilai Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

Variable	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Actual System Use_Y	0.633
Intention to Use_Z	0.627
Perceived Ease of Use_(X1)	0.570
Perceived Usefulness_(X2)	0.557

Source: SmartPLS data processing result, 2023

The Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value obtained from the analysis results is above 0.5, which is already said to be valid according to Fornell & Larcker (1981).

3.2. Discriminant Validity

Discriminant validity of constructs can be seen by comparing the AVE score of each construct with the correlation of other constructs. The results of the data analysis show that the AVE root of each construct exceeds the correlation between the construct and other constructs, so it can be said that the research model has good discriminant validity according to Fornell & Larcker (1981).

Table 2 Square Root of Average Variance Extracted

	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)	Square Root of AVE
<i>Actual System Use_Y</i>	0.633	0.796
<i>Intention to Use_Z</i>	0.627	0.792
<i>Perceived Ease of Use_X1</i>	0.570	0.755
<i>Perceived Usefulness_X2</i>	0.557	0.746

Source: SmartPLS data processing result, 2023

The AVE root acquisition is then used to see the results of the AVE root correlation between constructs. It can be seen in Table 3 that the AVE square root of each construct exceeds the correlation between variables, so it can be concluded that each variable already has high discriminant validity.

Table 3 Fornell-Larcker Criteria Discriminant Validity

	Actual System Use (Y)	Intention to Use (Z)	Perceived Ease of Use (X1)	Perceived Usefulness (X2)
Actual System Use (Y)	0.796			
Intention to Use (Z)	0.464	0.792		
Perceived Ease of Use (X1)	0.468	0.434	0.755	
Perceived Usefulness (X2)	0.486	0.406	0.419	0.747

Source: SmartPLS data processing result, 2023

The next discriminant validity test is conducted by looking at the output value of the Heterotrait-Monotrait (HTMT). To ensure discriminant validity between two reflective constructs, the HTMT value must be less than 0.9(21). The results of the analysis show that the results of discriminant validity have met based on the HTMT value.

Table 4 HTMT Evaluation

	Actual System Use (Y)	Intention to Use (Z)	Perceived Ease of Use (X1)	Perceived Usefulness (X2)
Actual System Use (Y)				
Intention to Use (Z)	0.571			
Perceived Ease of Use (X1)	0.559	0.478		
Perceived Usefulness (X2)	0.564	0.431	0.436	

Source: SmartPLS data processing result, 2023

3.3. Reliability Test

Reliability assessment is seen through Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability. Constructs are considered reliable if the Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability scores exceed 0.07 (22). The results of data analysis show that the Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability values have exceeded 0.7 as shown in Table 5.

Table 5 Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability

	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Description
Actual System Use_Y	0.713	0.838	Reliable
Intention to Use_Z	0.806	0.870	Reliable
Perceived Ease of Use_X1	0.925	0.936	Reliable
Perceived Usefulness_X2	0.928	0.938	Reliable

Source: SmartPLS data processing result, 2023

3.4. R-Square

Structural model testing is done by knowing the R-square value as a goodness fit model test (22).

Table 6 R-Square

	R-Square
Actual System Use (Y)	0.356
Intention to Use (Z)	0.250

Source: SmartPLS data processing result, 2023

Based on Table 6, it can be concluded that the variability of the actual system use construct that can be explained by perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness is 35.6% while the remaining 64.4% is explained by other variables that not examined in this study, and the variability of the intention to use construct that can be explained by the perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness variables is 25%, while the remaining 75% is explained by other variables that not examined in this study.

3.5. F-Square Effect Size

The F-Square effect size value categories are weak (0.02), medium (0.15), and strong (0.35).

Table 7 F-Square Effect Size

	Actual System Use (Y)	Intention to Use (Z)	Perceived Ease of Use (X1)	Perceived Usefulness (X2)
Actual System Use (Y)				
Intention to Use (Z)	0.070			
Perceived Ease of Use (X1)	0.069	0.113		
Perceived Usefulness (X2)	0.098	0.081		

Source: SmartPLS data processing result, 2023

Based on Table 7 above, it can be seen that there is a weak influence, namely intention to use on actual system use by 0.070, perceived ease of use on actual system use by 0.069, perceived usefulness on actual system use by 0.098, and perceived usefulness on intention to use by 0.081. In addition, there is also a medium effect, namely perceived ease of use on intention to use of 0.113.

3.6. Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis testing, which is known based on the significance value, is carried out to determine the effect between variables. Hypothesis testing can be determined by looking at the T-value and p-value in the bootstrapping calculation in SmartPLS 3.2.9.

Figure 3 Path Analysis Model Bootstrapping Results

Table 8 Direct Effect and Indirect Effect of Path Coefficient Output

	Original Sample	T-Statistic	P-Values	Description
<i>Direct Effect</i>				
Perceived Ease of Use (X1) → Actual System Use (Y)	0.243	3.217	0.001	H1 Accepted
Intention to Use (Z) → Actual System Use (Y)	0.243	2.764	0.006	H2 Accepted
Perceived Usefulness (X2) → Actual System Use (Y)	0.286	3.587	0.000	H3 Accepted
Perceived Ease of Use (X1) → Intention to Use (Z)	0.320	3.591	0.000	H4 Accepted
Perceived Usefulness (X2) → Intention to Use (Z)	0.272	2.874	0.004	H5 Accepted
<i>Indirect Effect</i>				
Perceived Ease of Use (X1) → Intention to Use (Z) → Actual System Use (Y)	0.078	1.973	0.049	H6 Accepted
Perceived Usefulness (X2) → Intention to Use (Z) → Actual System Use (Y)	0.066	2.020	0.049	H7 Accepted

Source: SmartPLS data processing result, 2023

Based on Table 8 above, the conclusions that can be drawn are:

H1: Perceived ease of use (X1) on actual system use (Y) has a positive effect with a score of 0.243, a t-statistic value of 3.217 > t table score of 1.98, and a p-value of 0.001 < from sig. 5%. This study proves that the perceived ease of use variable has a **positive and significant** effect on actual system use, so it can be concluded that **H1 is accepted**.

H2: Intention to use (Z) on actual system use (Y) has a positive effect with a score of 0.243, a t-statistic value of 2.764 > t table score of 1.98, and a p-value of 0.006 < from sig. 5%. This study proves that the intention to use variable has a **positive and significant** effect on actual system use, so it can be concluded that **H2 is accepted**.

H3: Perceived usefulness (X2) on actual system use (Y) has a positive effect with a score of 0.286, a t-statistic value of 3.587 > t table score of 1.98, and a p-value of 0.000 < from sig. 5%. This study proves that the perceived usefulness variable has a **positive and significant** effect on actual system use, so it can be concluded that **H3 is accepted**.

H4: Perceived ease of use (X1) on intention to use (Z) has a positive effect with a score of 0.320, a t-statistic value of 3.591 > t table score of 1.98, and a p-value of 0.000 < from sig. 5%. This study proves that the perceived ease of use variable has a **positive and significant** effect on intention to use, so it can be concluded that **H4 is accepted**.

H5: Perceived usefulness (X1) on intention to use (Z) has a positive effect with a score of 0.272, a t-statistic value of 2.874 > t table score of 1.98, and a p-value of 0.004 < from sig. 5%. This study proves that the perceived usefulness variable has a **positive and significant** effect on intention to use, so it can be concluded that **H5 is accepted**.

H6: The path coefficient of the perceived ease of use (X1) variable on actual system use (Y) through intention to use (Z) has a positive effect with a score of 0.078, a t-statistic value of 2.065 > t table score of 1.98, and a p-value of 0.047 < from sig. 5%. This study proves that the perceived ease of use variable has a **positive and significant** effect on actual system use through Intention to Use, so it can be concluded that **H6 is accepted**. Because both direct effect and indirect effect show significant results, the mediation relationship of intention to use as a mediating variable of perceived usefulness on actual system use is **partial mediation** in accordance with the mediation requirements according to Baron & Kenny (1986)(23).

H7: The path coefficient of the perceived usefulness (X2) variable on actual system use (Y) through intention to use (Z) has a positive effect with a score of 0.066, a t-statistic value of 2.020 > t table score of 1.98, and a p-value of 0.049 < from sig. 5%. This study proves that the perceived usefulness variable has a **positive and significant** effect on actual system use through intention to use, so it can be concluded that **H7 is accepted**. Because both direct effect and indirect effect show significant results, the mediation relationship of intention to use as a mediating variable of perceived usefulness on actual system use is **partial mediation** in accordance with the mediation requirements according to Baron & Kenny (1986)(23).

Table 9 Total Effect

<i>Direct Effect</i>	
Perceived Ease of Use (X1) → Actual System Use (Y)	0.243
Intention to Use (Z) → Actual System Use (Y)	0.243
Perceived Usefulness (X2) → Actual System Use (Y)	0.286
Perceived Ease of Use (X1) → Intention to Use (Z)	0.320
Perceived Usefulness (X1) → Intention to Use (Z)	0.272
<i>Indirect Effect</i>	
Perceived Ease of Use (X1) → Intention to Use (Z) → Actual System Use (Y)	0.078
Perceived Usefulness (X2) → Intention to Use (Z) → Actual System Use (Y)	0.066
<i>Total Effect</i>	
Perceived Ease of Use (X1) → Intention to Use (Z) → Actual System Use (Y) (0.243 + 0.078)	0.321
Perceived Usefulness (X2) → Intention to Use (Z) → Actual System Use (Y) (0.286 + 0.066)	0.352

Source: SmartPLS data processing result, 2023

Based on Table 9 above, it can be seen that the total effect for the indirect effect of Perceived Ease of Use (X1) on Actual System Use (Y) through Intention to Use (Z) is 0.321, greater than the direct effect of Perceived Ease of Use (X1) on Actual System Use (Y) of 0.243. This means that although perceived ease of use can have a significant effect on actual system use directly, the presence of intention to use as an intervening variable will have a greater effect than perceived ease of use on actual system use. Similarly, the total effect for the indirect effect of Perceived Usefulness (X2) on Actual System Use (Y) through Intention to Use (Z) is 0.352, greater than the direct effect of Perceived Usefulness (X2) on Actual System Use (Y) of 0.286, which means that although perceived usefulness can have a significant effect on actual system use directly, the presence of intention to use as an intervening variable will have a greater effect than perceived usefulness on actual system use.

4. Discussion

The results of direct effect testing show that perceived ease of use has a significant positive effect on actual system use, where the higher the perceived ease of use felt by users, the higher the actual system use. The results of this study are in line with research conducted by Haryani et al., (2014) and Harta Tira et al. (2016) which shows the results that perceived ease of use has a positive and significant effect on actual system use. The feeling of ease of use that users feel, such as easy to access, easy to understand how to use, and easy to interact with the system will make users continue to use the system which is reflected in the increasing frequency of use and the longer duration of use.

The results of direct effect testing show that intention to use has a positive and significant effect on actual system use, where the more perceived ease of use users feel, the more actual system use will increase. The results of this study are in line with research conducted by Andy et al., (2021) and Yuliana et al. (2022) which shows the results that intention to use has a positive and significant effect on actual system use. User interest in actually using Netflix arises when users have access to use Netflix, and movies/series that are being searched for or are of interest to users are available on Netflix, so users will spend their time using Netflix.

The results of direct effect testing show that perceived usefulness has a positive and significant effect on actual system use, where the higher the perceived ease of use felt by users, the higher the actual system use. The results of this study are in line with research conducted by Chairina (2021) and Harta Tira et al. (2016) which shows the results that perceived usefulness has a positive and significant effect on actual system use. The perceived benefits that users feel when using Netflix, such as increasing productivity, making it easier and faster to find movies/series, and being useful as a means of finding entertainment and learning, users will continue to use Netflix, which is reflected in the increasing frequency of use and the longer duration of use.

The results of direct effect testing perceived ease of use has a positive and significant effect on intention to use, where the higher the perceived ease of use felt by users, the higher the intention to use. The results of this study are in line with research conducted by Sindarta & Santoso (2022) and Lee et al. (2019) which shows the results that perceived ease of use has a positive and significant effect on intention to use. The feeling of ease of use that users feel, such as easy to access, easy to understand how to use, and easy to interact with the system will make users have an interest in using Netflix and plan to extend the Netflix subscription period.

The results of direct effect testing perceived usefulness has a positive and significant effect on intention to use, where the higher the perceived usefulness perceived by users, the higher the intention to use. The results of this study are in line with research conducted by Camilleri & Falzon (2021) and Sindarta & Santoso (2022) perceived usefulness has a positive and significant effect on intention to use. The benefits that users feel when using Netflix, such as a better viewing experience than conventional TV or other SVOD platforms, feeling increased productivity, speeding up movie/series searches, and being useful for finding entertainment and learning, then users will have an interest in using Netflix and plan to extend the Netflix subscription period.

The results of indirect effect testing perceived ease of use has a positive and significant effect on actual system use through intention to use as an intervening variable, where the higher the perceived ease of use felt by users, it will increase intention to use, which will then increase actual system use. The direct effect test shows that perceived ease of use has a positive and significant effect on actual system use, so it can be concluded that the mediating relationship between intention to use is partial mediation. This is in line with research by Rahmawati & Narsa (2019), where intention to use acts as a partial mediating variable between perceived ease of use and actual system use(19).

The results of indirect effect testing perceived usefulness has a positive and significant effect on actual system use through intention to use as an intervening variable, where the higher the perceived usefulness perceived by users, it will increase intention to use, which will then increase actual system use. The direct effect test shows that perceived usefulness has a positive and significant effect on actual system use, so it can be concluded that the mediating relationship between intention to use is partial mediation. This is in line with research by Rahmawati & Narsa (2019), where intention to use acts as a partial mediating variable between perceived usefulness and actual system use.

5. Conclusion

- The perceived ease of use (X1) variable has a positive and significant effect on the Actual system use (Y) variable on the Netflix service. This can be interpreted that a positive perception of ease of use can increase the amount of time users spend using the Netflix service.
- The intention to use (Z) variable has a positive and significant effect on the actual system use (Y) variable. This means that when respondents have an interest in doing something, in this case having an interest in using Netflix, the respondents will use it. This use is reflected in the frequency and duration of time spent using Netflix.
- The perceived usefulness (X1) variable has a positive and significant effect on the actual system use (Y) variable. This can be interpreted that a positive perception of the benefits obtained by users while using Netflix or after using Netflix can increase the amount of time users spend using Netflix services.
- The perceived ease of use variable (X1) has a positive and significant effect on the intention to use variable (Z). This can be interpreted that a positive perception of the ease of use of Netflix will lead to an interest in using Netflix..
- The perceived usefulness variable (X1) has a positive and significant effect on the intention to use variable (Z). This can be interpreted that a positive perception of the benefits provided when using Netflix or after using Netflix will generate interest in using Netflix.
- The mediation relationship between the perceived ease of use (X1) variable and actual system use (Y) through the intention to use (Z) variable on the Netflix service is partial mediation. This is because both directly and indirectly, perceived ease of use can affect actual system use with a positive and significant effect..
- The mediation relationship between the perceived usefulness (X2) variable and actual system use (Y) through the intention to use (Z) variable on the Netflix service is partial mediation. This is because both directly and indirectly, perceived usefulness can affect actual system use with a positive and significant effect.

Suggestions

- The research results related to perceived ease of use where many respondents had problems understanding the process of purchasing a Netflix subscription package and how to cancel a Netflix subscription package. This is because there is no example of how to use Netflix from start to finish so users do not know the process to go through to pay for a subscription package or cancel it. The countermeasure for this problem is that the company can provide a tutorial on how to use Netflix from start to finish. This tutorial will be useful for users, especially for new users to better understand how to use Netflix.
- The research results related to perceived usefulness where many respondents had problems with performance in finding movies/series, the motivation provided from using Netflix, Netflix as a means to learn about other cultures, finding movies/series based on preferences, and the benefits of Netflix as an educational spectacle. The countermeasure for this problem is that the company can increase the content provided on the Netflix platform, because many of the shows sought by users are available on other countries' regional Netflix but are not available in Indonesia. The content should be in line with the values of the community and not controversial.
- The results of research related to intention to use where respondents are less interested in continuing to subscribe to Netflix if the subscription package is more expensive. So Netflix needs to pay attention to the pricing strategy so that the price offered can still be reached by its target market. Netflix's price increase must be adjusted to improve the quality of the products they offer, such as routine maintenance and adding to the collection of shows on its platform, such as movies/series that are requested by users.
- The results of research related to actual system use where most respondents use Netflix in the frequency category which is quite rare, as well as the duration of use which is in the short category because users do not always have free time to use Netflix every day, but still take the time to use Netflix at least once a week. To increase user session time on the application, a check in feature can be created, a reminder feature to continue watching, and also add new movies/series that are being searched for by the majority of users, so that users have a reason to log in and use Netflix on a daily frequency.
- Future research can add the Attitude Toward Using variable as one of the constructs used in the Technology Acceptance Model in order to better explain the variability of Actual System Use and Intention to Use.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

The authors would like to thank Department of Business Administration, Diponegoro University and all parties involved in this research.

Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interest exists.

References

- [1] Lee C. C, Lim HS. FACTORS AFFECTING OVER-THE-TOP SERVICES : AN EXPANDED TECHNOLOGY ACCEPTANCE MODEL. *Int J Interdisciplinary Res.* 2019;8(1).
- [2] Pratama DY, Iqbal IM, Tarigan NA. Makna Televisi Bagi Generasi Z. 2019;4(1):88–103.
- [3] Ketut Agustini, I Nengah Suparta, I Made Gede Sunarya IMAW. BERBASIS MOBILE UNTUK PELAKU PARIWISATA DI KABUPATEN BULELENG DENGAN MODEL TAM. *J Ilm Teknol Inf.* 2014;3(1):300–10.
- [4] Fishbein M, Ajzen I. Belief, Attitude, Intention, and Behavior: An Introduction to Theory and Research. Ajzen I, editor. Boston: Addison-Wesley Publishing Company; 1975. 578 p.
- [5] Jogyanto. Sistem Informasi Keperilakuan (Edisi Revisi). Yogyakarta: Andi Offset; 2007.
- [6] Davis FD. A Technology Acceptance Model for Empirically Testing New End-User Information Systems: Theory and Results. 1986.
- [7] Davis FD, Bagozzi RP, Warshaw PR. User Acceptance of Computer Technology: A Comparison of Two Theoretical Models. *Manage Sci.* 1989;35(8):982–1003.
- [8] Money W, Turner A. Application of the technology acceptance model to a knowledge management system. *Proc Hawaii Int Conf Syst Sci.* 2004;37(C):3707–15.
- [9] Venkatesh V, Davis FD. Theoretical extension of the Technology Acceptance Model: Four longitudinal field studies. *Manage Sci.* 2000;46(2):186–204.
- [10] Davis FD. User acceptance of information technology: system characteristics, user perceptions and behavioral impacts. Vol. 38, *International Journal of Man-Machine Studies.* 1993. p. 475–87.
- [11] Igarria M, Iivari J. The Effects of Self-Efficacy on Computer Usage. *Omega.* 1995;23(6):587–605.
- [12] Haryani D, A MS, Pujani V. E-Travel Use in Padang: The Role of Enjoyment, Perceived Ease of Use, and Perceived Usefulness. In: *International Conference on Business, Management, & Corporate Social Responsibility (ICBMCSR'14).* 2014. p. 64–8.
- [13] Harta Tira ACD, Wardana IM, Setiawan PY. Aplikasi Model TAM pada Penggunaan E-Newspaper di Kota Denpasar. *E-Jurnal Ekon dan Bisnis Univ Udayana.* 2016;5(6):1485–512.
- [14] Andy R, Dewi AC, As'adi M. An Empirical Study to Validate The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) In Evaluating “Desa Digital” Applications. *IOP Conf Ser Mater Sci Eng.* 2021;1125(1):012055.
- [15] Yuliana K, Syarwani A, Helda. Acceptance Analysis of School DAPODIK Information System Using the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM). In: *International Seminar on Education, Technology, and Art.* 2022. p. 114–23.
- [16] Chairina RRL. The Effect of Perceived Usefulness and Perceived Ease of Use on Perceived Value and Actual Usage of Technology on the Online Service of Pt. Garuda Indonesia Tbk. *Quest Journals J Res Bus Manag [Internet].* 2021;9(4):2347–3002. Available from: www.questjournals.org
- [17] Sindarta F, Santoso T. Pengaruh Perceived Ease of Use terhadap Intention to Use Melalui Perceived Usefulness Aplikasi Pemutar Musik Spotify di Kalangan Pengguna Smartphone Berbasis Android. *AGORA.* 2022;10(1).
- [18] Camilleri MA, Falzon L. Understanding Motivations to Use Online Streaming Services: Integrating The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) and The Uses and Gratifications Theory (UGT). *Spanish J Mark - ESIC.* 2021;25(2):216–36.

- [19] Rahmawati RN, Narsa IM. Actual Usage Penggunaan E-Learning dengan Technology Acceptance Model. *J Inov Teknol Pendidik* [Internet]. 2019;6(2):127–36. Available from: <http://journal.uny.ac.id/index.php/jitp>
- [20] Fornell C, Larcker D. Structural Equation Models with Unobservable Variables and Measurement Error; *Algebra and Statistic*. *J Mark Res*. 1981;18:382–8.
- [21] Hanseler J, Ringle C., Sarsdedt M. A new criterion for assessing discriminant validity in variance-based structural equation modeling. *J Acad Mark Sci*. 2015;43(1):115–35.
- [22] Ghozali I, Latan H. *Konsep, Teknik, Aplikasi Menggunakan Smart PLS 3.0 Untuk Penelitian Empiris*. Semarang: Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro; 2015.
- [23] Baron R, Kenny D. The moderator–mediator variable distinction in social psychological research: Conceptual, strategic, and statistical considerations. *J Pers Soc Psychol*. 1986;51(6):1173–82.